

In Situ Grazing Incidence Small-Angle X-ray Scattering Investigation of Polystyrene Nanoparticle Spray Deposition onto Silicon

Gerd Herzog,^{*,†,‡} Gunthard Benecke,^{†,§} Adeline Buffet,[†] Berit Heidmann,[†] Jan Perlich,[†] Johannes F. H. Risch,[†] Gonzalo Santoro,[†] Matthias Schwartzkopf,[†] Shun Yu,[†] Wilfried Wurth,[‡] and Stephan V. Roth^{*,†}

[†]Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY), Notkestrasse 85, D-22607 Hamburg, Germany

[‡]Universität Hamburg, Department Physik, Institut für Experimentalphysik, Luruper Chaussee 149, D-22761 Hamburg, Germany

[§]MPI of Colloids and Interfaces, Department of Biomaterials, Am Mühlenberg 1, D-14476 Potsdam-Golm, Germany

We investigated the spray deposition and subsequent self-assembly during drying of a polystyrene nanoparticle dispersion with in situ grazing incidence small-angle X-ray scattering at high time resolution. During the fast deposition of the dispersion and the subsequent evaporation of the solvent, different transient stages of nanoparticle assembly can be identified. In the *first* stage, the solvent starts to evaporate without ordering of the nanoparticles. During the second stage, large-scale structures imposed by the breakup of the liquid *film* are observable. In this stage, the solvent evaporates further and nanoparticle ordering starts. In the late third drying stage, thenanoparticles self-assemble into the *final* layer structure.

INTRODUCTION

Surface coating is a task that occurs often and for many purposes in industry and research as well as in everyday life. It can be accomplished by a multitude of methods like solution-casting,^{1,2} printing,^{3,4} painting, spin-coating,^{5,6} dip-coating,⁷ and spray-coating.^{8–11} In this study, we focus on spray-coating as it can offer a fast, easy, economic, and reproducible method for coating surfaces. It is used for applications like water-repellent paper,¹² electrolyte *films*,^{13,14} semiconductors,¹⁵ LEDs,^{16,17} transistors,¹⁸ sensing units (e-tongue systems),¹⁹ and solar cells.^{20–25} Spray-coating can be used for conventional solutions, colloidal nanoparticle dispersions, and wet powder suspensions. Research has been done on the spray deposition process as such^{8–10} and on colloidal droplet evaporation in general.^{1,2,26–38} Colloidal systems are heavily used as thin *films* and templates³⁹ or in nanocomposites in the areas mentioned above and furthermore to produce even three-dimensional structures.^{40,41} We would like to mention that the use of colloids in functional thin *films* allows the design of a controlled roughness that can be used, for instance, to increase the light harvesting *efficiency* in organic solar cells.⁴² Therefore, it is mandatory to improve our understanding of the kinetics during the installation of the thin *film*.

Often, the evaporation of colloidal dispersions has been investigated in the context of subsequent particle deformation and coalescence leading to the formation of a mechanically coherent *film*.^{43–45} Some of these investigations have been

performed above the glass transition temperature (T_g) of a polymeric latex *film*.^{46,47}

In this study, we investigate the spray deposition of an aqueous dispersion of polystyrene nanoparticles at room temperature (RT), i.e., far below the T_g of polystyrene. We therefore focus on the deposition of individual nanoparticles and their self-assembly process. Our aim is to resolve the general drying procedures of the nanoparticle dispersion and the installation of the self-assembled ordered nanoparticle thin *film*. One method of choice for investigating in situ dynamic processes and rapid kinetics especially during self-assembly on the nanoscale is grazing incidence small-angle X-ray scattering (GISAXS).^{1,48–53} We therefore employed a novel in situ setup, combining GISAXS and spray deposition.^{8,9} Because of the high brilliance of the third-generation synchrotron source, we were able to obtain a subsecond time resolution and to identify the three basic steps related to spray deposition and subsequent drying of the dispersion leading to self-assembly of the nanoparticles.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Sample Preparation. Silicon wafer pieces (Si-Mat, 26 mm × 76 mm) were stored in a dichloromethane bath at RT for 30 min and transferred into deionized water for 20 min and then into a basic

bath⁵⁴ consisting of 525 mL of deionized water, 46 mL of a 30% ammonia solution, and 47 mL of 30% hydrogen peroxide at 65 °C. The basic bath was heated to 75 °C for 2 h. The wafer pieces were then rinsed with deionized water and dried with nitrogen. This cleaning procedure led to a hydrophilic substrate surface. As a colloidal sample, we employed commercially available polystyrene (PS) nanoparticles (Kisker Biotech, nominal diameter of 100 nm, dispersed in water). The particle surface is functionalized by a very low level of sulfate groups. As part of the production process, the dispersion contains surfactants. The initial dispersion was diluted using ethanol to obtain a mixture with a volume ratio of 60% ethanol and 40% water. The PS concentration was ~ 1 vol %. The addition of ethanol allows for tuning of the solvent evaporation rate. Such nanoparticles are ideal model systems for observing order phenomena^{55–57} and are employed, e.g., in organic photovoltaics to create tailor-made porosities.⁴²

Grazing Incidence Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (GISAXS) Measurements. GISAXS measurements were performed on beamline P03⁵⁸ of the PETRA III storage ring of DESY (Hamburg, Germany). A two-dimensional (2D) detector (Pilatus 1M, 981 \times 1043 pixels, pixel size of 172 $\mu\text{m} \times$ 172 μm) was used at a sample-to-detector distance of 4000 mm. The X-ray beam had a wavelength λ of 0.0957 nm and a beam size of 25 μm (horizontal) \times 13 μm (vertical), and the angle of incidence (α_i) was set to 0.45°. This angle is well above the critical angle of the materials involved and allows thus a clear separation of the Yoneda⁵⁹ region and the specular beam stop. Therefore, we are able to obtain full 2D GISAXS patterns with minimal shadowing by beam stops and gaining access to the region around $q_y = 0 \text{ nm}^{-1}$.⁴⁸ A commercial airbrush (Harder & Steenbeck model Grafo T3) was installed at the beamline and operated at a pressure of 1 bar. The distance between the spray nozzle and sample was 10 cm with a PTFE mask (thickness of 1 cm, slit size of 0.5 cm \times 2 cm) between them. A sketch of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. The PS nanoparticle/ethanol/water dispersion was sprayed

Figure 1. Sketch of the grazing incidence small-angle X-ray scattering

(GISAXS) setup. α_i denotes the incident angle, α_f the exit angle, and

2Θ the out-of-plane angle. q_y and q_z denote the horizontal and vertical components, respectively, of the scattering vector. SBS denotes the specular beam stop, IDG the intermodular detector gap, SN the spray nozzle, and M the mask.

onto the sample within 0.1 s. During the spraying and the subsequent drying process, GISAXS patterns were recorded at a rate of 2 frames/s. Simultaneously, a video was recorded with an optical camera (Watek).

Atomic Force Microscopy and Optical Microscopy. After the spraying experiment, atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements were performed using an NT-MDT NTEGRA Aura System. The sample was probed via tapping mode under ambient conditions in air.

Several different spots on the sample were probed at different scan sizes. The sample was also examined via optical microscopy (Keyence VHX-600) to observe the large-scale, macroscopic structure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The in situ GISAXS experiment yielded a series of 2D GISAXS patterns. Exemplary patterns for the dried state can be seen on the right side of Figure 1 and in Figure 2a. These patterns show a specular beam stop (SBS) that shielded the specular peak (in the top central part) to prevent saturation or damage of the detector as its intensity is several orders of magnitude higher than that of the diffuse scattering in the rest of the pattern. The horizontal black bar is caused by the intermodular detector gap (IDG) between adjacent modules of the detector. The vertical streak in the center of the pattern indicates the reflection plane; i.e., the horizontal component of the scattering wave vector q_y equals zero ($q_y = 0$). In the lower part of this streak, one can see an intensity maximum, the Yoneda⁵⁹ peak, which occurs at the critical angle of the scattering material. In the patterns depicting the spray-coated sample in the dried state, side maxima can be observed on both sides of the Yoneda peak. These side maxima indicate the most prominent length scale of the PS nanoparticle assembly corresponding to the nearest-neighbor distance between the ordered nanoparticles. To give a qualitative overview of the experiment, a video sequence showing the 2D GISAXS patterns during spray deposition and subsequent drying as well as an optical video can be found in the Supporting Information.

To analyze these patterns in more detail, horizontal cuts called out-of-plane^{48,60} cuts were taken at the Yoneda peak with DPDAK (freely available at <http://www.desy.de/~beneckeg/dpdak>). To improve the statistics, these were integrated over 10 pixels. This area is indicated by the red rectangle in Figure 2a. Out-of-plane cuts for the first 20 s of the experiment are shown as a map in Figure 2b. Purely qualitatively, one can already identify three stages of structure formation after the very first cut, which is depicting the spraying. From the second cut on, the substrate surface is covered with liquid and the scattering intensity diminishes. After approximately 6 s, an intermediate stage is reached with a higher intensity at and around the Yoneda peak. Finally, after ~ 13 s, the substrate surface is dry and the two side maxima emerge and indicate the nearest-neighbor distance between the nanoparticles that, for close packing, equals the particle diameter. Figure 2c shows an individual cut of the dry stage at the time indicated with the solid white vertical line in Figure 2b.

The out-of-plane cuts of the first 20 s are also displayed in Figure 3a. The cuts are shifted vertically for the sake of clarity. One can easily identify the early wet stage with a rather slim Yoneda peak, the intermediate stage with a broader peak, and the dry stage with side maxima at $q_y \approx \pm 0.07 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ that indicate the nearest-neighbor distance $d = 2\pi/q_y \approx 90 \text{ nm}$. This corresponds well with the nominal nanoparticle diameter of 100 nm that was measured with dynamic light scattering in solution and thus is a hydrodynamic diameter including a hydration shell. In Figure 3b, we present averaged cuts of the three regions to represent these regions.

To follow the drying kinetics quantitatively, we further analyzed the q range around the side maxima at $q_y \approx 0.07 \text{ nm}^{-1}$. Obviously, the intensity change in this q range is strongly correlated with the self-assembly of the PS nanoparticles. To do so, a Lorentzian curve was fit to this q range at a fixed position of $q_y = 0.067 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ to extract the intensity change in this q

Figure 2. (a) Exemplary two-dimensional (2D) GISAXS pattern of the dried sample. SBS denotes the specular beam stop and IDG the intermodular detector gap. q_y and q_z denote the horizontal and vertical components, respectively, of the scattering vector, and ROI denotes the central part of the region of interest whose integrated intensity is plotted in Figure 4. The horizontal red rectangle indicates the region integrated for the out-of-plane cuts. The red arrows mark the position of side maxima indicating the distance of the colloidal nanoparticles. (b) Map of out-of-plane cuts as a function of time. The vertical dotted lines indicate the transition from the early stage I to intermediate stage II and to final dried stage III. The solid white line marks the time at which the out-of-plane cut shown in panel c was taken. (c) Individual out-of-plane cut of the dried sample displaying side maxima corresponding to the most prominent lateral length scale of ~ 90 nm.

region and then to quantify the amplitude of this side maximum, which indicates the nanoparticle deposition and ordering in the *fluid* phase. This parameter is plotted in Figure 4 as a function of time.

The amplitude rises steeply after 6 s, showing both a local maximum and a local minimum, and levels off to its plateau value caused by the ordered dry structure. Additionally, we show the integrated intensity of a region of interest (ROI) consisting of a vertical cut around $q_y = 0$ (detector cut) with a width of 11 pixels in red. This ROI is indicated by red vertical lines in Figure 2a. Both the red and the blue curves show relatively low values for the early wet stage (which can be explained by X-ray absorption by the liquid), an increase followed by fluctuations during the intermediate stage and a rapid change toward a stable dry stage. For the blue curve, the increase from the early wet stage toward the intermediate stage occurs later than for the red curve. This indicates that the ordering of the nanoparticles only starts rapidly after a certain amount of solvent has evaporated.

Figure 5 shows the Yoneda peak region of *off*-detector (vertical) cuts taken at the position of the side maxima at $q_y = 0.067 \text{ nm}^{-1}$. The green curve shows a cut taken of the pure silicon substrate before the experiment. The lower (red) curve shows the average of 11 cuts taken within 5.5 s of deposition. The blue curve shows the average of 14 cuts taken during the subsequent 7 s of an intermediate stage. The upper (black) curve shows the average of 15 cuts taken during the following 7.5 s, representing the same kinetic regions as in Figure 3b. The four curves are clearly distinct. When the dry stage is reached, a new peak around 0.1° emerges, corresponding to the deposition of the PS nanoparticles. The intensity around 0.13° , the Yoneda peak of silicon, also increases further because of the correlated roughness of the installed nanoparticle *film*.

On the basis of the observations described above, we propose the following model, sketched in Figure 6. Directly after spray deposition, a liquid *film* is installed on the Si surface. This

structureless homogeneous *film* leads to the scattering pattern in Figure 6a (region I). As one can see from the optical microscopy video in the Supporting Information, the *film* drying is nonhomogeneous and leads to a breakup into small droplets. These droplets contain colloidal particles and liquid. Because of the *finite* resolution of this experimental GISAXS setup, these structures are not resolved, and their size and distribution lead to a broadening of the central Yoneda peak in Figure 6b (region II). Finally, the droplets dry and the installed colloidal structure shows up as side maxima in the scattering pattern in Figure 6c, defining region III. Because of the ordered nanostructure, the intensity is shifted from the central peak around $q_y = 0 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ to the side maxima, which is one of the reasons for the strong decrease in the integrated intensity around $q_y = 0 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 7 shows an AFM topography image of a $1 \mu\text{m} \times 1 \mu\text{m}$ area after spray deposition. Here, we clearly identify the colloidal arrangement and observe domains of PS colloids on the order of $1 \mu\text{m}$, which are not resolved with this experimental GISAXS setup. We may speculate that the deposited domains occur as indicated by Bigioni et al.²⁸ on the surface of the individual droplets after breakup of the liquid *film*, which might also contribute to the observed broadening of the Yoneda peak. An optical microscopy image of the spray-coated sample can be found in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information. The part of the sample that has been covered by a continuous liquid *film* is surrounded by individual dried droplets. Our GISAXS investigation was conducted in the area that was fully covered with liquid.

In previous experiments, often drop casting was investigated. Roth et al.¹ performed an *in situ* GISAXS investigation of the drying of a single droplet containing an aqueous dispersion of gold nanoparticles. For the single deposited droplet, two stages during slow drying were observed, namely, a lateral ordering followed by vertical layer-by-layer growth. This vertical growth might be caused by a higher concentration and also by a larger

Figure 3. (a) Out-of-plane cuts of 40 GISAXS patterns representing the first 20 s after spraying. One can easily identify an early stage with a slim Yoneda peak, an intermediate stage with a wider peak, and the dry stage with two side maxima. (b) Averaged out-of-plane cuts taken during the first 20 s after spraying, representing the three stages of structure formation: the first 5.5 s after spraying, the subsequent 7 s during the intermediate stage, and the following 7.5 s of the dry stage.

Figure 4. Blue diagonal crosses depict the amplitude of a Lorentzian fit to the side maximum in the out-of-plane cuts shown in Figure 3a. The red plus signs indicate the integrated intensity of a region of interest around the detector cut as a function of time after spraying. The central part of this region of interest is displayed in Figure 2a. I, II, and III mark the early, intermediate, and dry stages of film formation, respectively. While both parameters show strong fluctuations during the first two stages, their values are almost constant once the sample has dried.

Figure 5. Yoneda region in off-detector cuts taken at the position of the side maxima as a function of time. The green curve shows a cut taken of the pure silicon substrate before the experiment. The lowest (red) curve shows the average of 11 cuts taken within 5.5 s of deposition. The blue curve shows the average of 14 cuts taken during the subsequent 7 s of an intermediate stage. The upper (black) curve shows the average of 15 cuts taken during the following 7.5 s. While the intensity around an exit angle $\alpha_f = 0.05^\circ$ did not change much as compared to the blue curve, the intensity around 0.13° has increased further. This region corresponds to the Yoneda peak of silicon. A clear intensity change at 0.05° is also observed between the green curve and the blue and black curves, which we attribute to the form factor of the PS colloids.

amount of liquid per substrate area, as only a single droplet was deposited. Sen et al.²⁹ performed a SAXS investigation of the drying of silica colloids in water droplets at elevated temperatures under a nitrogen flow. They report on homogeneous and inhomogeneous drying. The spray-coating performed in our experiment can be considered a very fast process, and we estimate the Peclet number to be >1 . Accompanied by a dewetting phenomenon as depicted in Figure 6 and observable in the optical video in the Supporting Information, we may speculate that – also following the work of Bigioni et al.²⁸ – inhomogeneous drying seems to be predominant. Merlin et al.⁵³ conducted a SAXS experiment on the evaporation of an aqueous colloidal silica dispersion using a microevaporator. They observed an increase in the concentration prior to solidification. We may assume that such an increase in concentration leads to the development of the side maxima in our GISAXS patterns. Al-Hussein et al.⁹ used in situ GISAXS to investigate the spray deposition and subsequent drying of an aqueous dispersion of gold nanoparticles on top of a conducting polymer. They observed a buckling of the Au nanoparticle layer, which we did not observe. This is due to the different substrate (silicon) used here. Hu et al.³⁰ and Chen et al.⁶¹ investigated the drying of droplets of aqueous dispersions of colloidal polymer nanoparticles with SAXS and determined that the particles form fcc structures after drying. While we used an initial solid content of ~ 1 wt %, Hu et al. and Chen et al. used higher concentrations of 40 and ~ 30 wt %, respectively. Instead of investigating the evaporation of liquid concentrated in one droplet, we watched the drying of a tiny amount of liquid spread across an area ~ 10 mm in diameter. In combination with the far lower initial concentration, this led to a predominantly 2D structure. As one can see in Figure 7, the substrate is not fully covered with nanoparticles. We used IsGISAXS⁶² by Lazzari to simulate out-of-plane cuts for 2D

Figure 6. Three exemplary 2D GISAXS patterns representing the three stages of drying and corresponding real-space sketches of the sample surface covered with liquid and/or PS nanoparticles.

Figure 7. AFM topography image ($1 \mu\text{m} \times 1 \mu\text{m}$) showing individual PS nanoparticles on the silicon substrate.

hexagonal and cubic lattices and compared them to out-of-plane cuts of our GISAXS patterns. The simulations hint at a hexagonal structure.

CONCLUSION

To summarize, we investigated the spray deposition and subsequent drying process of a polystyrene nanoparticle dispersion on a silicon substrate with in situ GISAXS and identified an early drying state, an intermediate drying state, and a final drying state. The in situ GISAXS observations correspond well with the optical investigation, conducted in parallel during the GISAXS experiment. On the basis of these observations, we develop a model for describing these three stages. Directly after spray deposition, the first state corresponds to a structureless thin liquid film, which breaks up and allows for possible transient nanoparticle ordering in the intermediate state. During the late stages of drying, the PS colloids self-assemble, and thus, the colloidal nanostructure is installed. The knowledge of these three basic steps is very important for process technology in, e.g., organic electronics or photovoltaics, as it is ideally suited for the rapid installation of tailored functional thin films with specific properties.

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